

In the aesthetic culture of medieval Azerbaijan, as well as Nakhchivan, architecture, decorative applied art, and miniature art had socio-philosophical meaning. In miniatures, color absorbs light, becomes transparent, and shines without shadows. In the miniatures, the light seems to be resolved by one color, the expression of the spatial values falls under the responsibility of the color, and the aerial perspective is eliminated. Patterns complementing the images were applied in abundance in this art. Among those who gave these pearls during the formation of miniature art were miniaturist Soltan Muhammad, Kamaladdin Behzad, Abdulmomin Muhammad al-Khoyi, Mirza Ali, Muzaffar Ali, Sadiq Bey Afshar, etc, occupied an exceptional place.

The widespread spread of ornamental art in the Muslim countries of the Near and Middle East, as well as in Nakhchivan, and the attempts to turn the ornament into a meaningful sign by moving from ornament to writing, from writing to ornament, created a philosophical meaning in the patterns. As researchers have shown, the geometric patterns created in this period can be considered an integral form for the spirit of Islam. Ceremonies, which are a branch of national moral values, are repeated rhythmically in the public space, and certain patterns remain unchanged in patterns, which

reflects the synthesis of our national moral values. Thus, ornamental art in all Muslim countries, including Nakhchivan, is connected to serious socio-philosophical roots. Researchers see geometric shapes as symbols of absolute existence. The fact that ornaments, which are part of the national architectural culture of Nakhchivan, are often repeated in science as symbols of religious and philosophical meanings is a fundamental issue of our architectural theory.

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CREATIVE ATTITUDE TO MINIATURE AESTHETICS

Ismayilov J.

*Dean of Art faculty, Nakhchivan State University
Nakhchivan city, Azerbaijan*

Abstract

The sixties-eighties stage of Azerbaijani painting, which has an ancient history and rich artistic traditions, was also characterized by appeals to national traditions by artists of different ages. One of such creators was Yuran Mammadov (1934-1984), who lived and created in Nakhchivan. The young artist who studied in Baku and St. Petersburg and is deeply familiar with the traditions of realism, unlike many others, preferred to create paintings with modern themes and different genres with a creative attitude to the miniature style, which has ancient traditions. Yuran Mammadov, who tried himself in the art of painting, graphics and theater decoration in his 22-year career, left behind him an artistic heritage that could literally enrich the 20th century Azerbaijani fine art. "Afternoon", "By the spring" and "Portrait of my son", a creative approach to the aesthetics of the classic miniature style can be heard in the paintings. This can be observed both in the artistic solution of the works and in the use of contrasting shades of colors that give the compositions a national flavor.

Keywords: classic, tradition, miniature, contrast, heritage, aesthetics, theme, genre.

Since the teaching process in the first art school established in Baku after the occupation of Azerbaijan by the 11th Army was conducted on the basis of the artistic principle of "socialist realism" corresponding to the Soviet ideology, the students created their creative examples directly by following the traditions of realism. Despite this, the school's young graduates also showed an example of returning to their roots - benefiting from the miniature style - in their post-educational pursuits. This was considered to be a direct reflection of the desire to deviate from the demands of the "tops" - Kremlin ideologues. Therefore, it was expected that it would not go unanswered. In the exhibition held in Baku in 1934 on the occasion of the 1000th anniversary of the birth of such a famous poet Ferdovsi, the works by young Azerbaijani artists (Alekbard Rzagaluyev,

Salam Salamzade, Gazanfar Khaligov, Amir Hajiyev, etc.) were criticized for returning to the ancient artistic tradition. When recalling the repression of the thirties, it can be considered understandable that the others, except for A.Rzagaluyev, moved away from the miniature [2]. A. Rzagaluyev's 28 years of exile and prison life after that can be considered as an image of the current regime's attitude towards this issue. However, it should be said that the miniature style, which has been confirmed for a long time, has become a reliable moral support for the artistic pursuits of several Azerbaijani artists even in the historicized 20th century. It is a good thing that the artists of Nakhchivan have from time to time creatively benefited from this timeless style and have created works of various genres that bring to life

the unity of tradition and modernity. Among such artists, it is possible to name many artists, including Yuran Mammadov. Yuran Mammadov, who studied under V. Oreshnikov, who was considered one of the outstanding followers of the school of realism, at the Institute of Painting, Sculpture and Architecture named after I. Y. Repin, which was considered very influential in the USSR at the time, decided not to return to Azerbaijan after his studies, but decided to stay in St. Petersburg (former Leninrad). The artist, who started working as a designer-artist at the famous "Aleksandrov Theater" in the city, also finds time to do easel painting and graphics. This period can be considered as the stage of his formation as an artist. Those who knew the young artist closely hoped that he would be a follower of the traditions of realism as a student of V. Oreshnikov.

However, his creative search and his first works, which were the results of this, showed that he was far from continuing the path of realism. Although some have said that there are similarities between the various genre works created by the artist and the works belonging to the movement of post-impressionism and fauvism, such hasty conclusions did not actually reflect the real truth. Thus, in the works of P. Gauguin and A. Matisse, who are considered to be the most advanced representatives of those trends, the aesthetics of East-Azerbaijani miniatures was prominently felt. Thus, these artists' familiarity with miniatures at the "Muslim art" exhibitions organized in Europe in the 19th and 20th centuries radically changed their world views and palettes [3]. That is why "researchers" who are not aware of Azerbaijani miniatures, instead of emphasizing that Yura appealed to the classical tradition - national roots, linked it to Western painting was a wrong assessment.

If we talk about the artistic features of the "Leningrad period" work of the young artist, then first of all, it is possible to see a fascinating set of "composites" created from contrasting colors, in addition to the "play" of scale in these works, which are dominated by decorativeness, as in miniatures. In other words, the achievement of intra-compositional size and spatial image by "matching" color surfaces was primarily the result of a creative attitude to the classical heritage. It was a good thing that those painting and graphics samples were not considered miniatures, but were perceived as works that make the artist's "I" alive. Indeed, the rhythm and expressiveness of the forms, which are "enriched" from the decorativeness of colors, are masterly in the fluidity of the overall image. The appeal of the compositions as a whole, as it was "melted", was as enchanting as in the miniatures. Later, the artist's friend Anar, appreciating the artistic merits we have highlighted, would say that the aesthetics in Yura's works do not fit the canons of classicism...

It was possible to witness the oriental spirit of the scenery in the arrangements he gave to A. Nesi's "Tarus monster" and A. Sagareli's "Khanuma" performances in the Alexandrov Theater [1]. After education, the artist directed the academic artistic skills he acquired in the theaters of the "Northern capital" to increase the artistic performance of the performances, and then performed this work in his native Nakhchivan theater for nearly 20 years. He was featured in most of his works here,

including "Tbilisi yengeri" (A. Sagareli), "Haji Gambar" (N.B. Vazirov), "The Great Wave of the Ganges" (J. Afruz), etc. there were quite a lot of moments that resonated with the aesthetics of paintings in the arrangements he gave to the performances. Let's admit, Yuran Mammadov's influence on dramaturgical material and giving an artistic appearance to the literary text was different and unique from the artistic approach observed in the performances of the theater until then. However, he remained in the memory of his colleagues and art lovers as an artist with an individual and different artistic thinking...

The main reason for this was that he found national sources in his artistic search, far from being captured by known "isms" like many others in his time. Here, if we remember that Yura's arrival to great art in the early sixties - the "hard style" influenced the local and former USSR space, then it can be considered very logical that the young artist found the aesthetics of miniature and handmade art and showed a creative attitude to known spiritual sources. The closeness of the young artist with Sattar Bahlulzade and Togrul Narimanbeyov, who gained enough fame for their works of national spirit created in the space of the former USSR, further strengthened the process of his development of a different view of reality with miniature aesthetics. In other words, this rich source allowed the artist to directly express the creative power he carried in his soul, in the form of a set of details inspired by the national spirit. After the artist's return to his native Nakhchivan, from the country's childhood the places he immortalized in the memory of the eye were immortalized on canvas with great enthusiasm. His "Hachadag", "Batabat", "Alinja Castle", "Vaykhur Village", "Araz", "Shahbuz View", "Spring in Nakhchivan", "Village", "Awakening" etc. the tableaus became a visual image of this. The prominent writer Anar, who became a close friend of the artist, characterizes his work "Awakening" as follows: "Awakening" depicts a spring landscape. The trunks of the trees are still dark in color and look a bit dull. Despite this, the branches that draw the juice of the earth to their chests, being soaked in spring colors, indicate the awakening of life. The elk and its owner, moving forward with agile steps, the cloudy spring sky and the entire atmosphere of the painting evoke in the viewer joyful and optimistic feelings about the renewal of life [4,444].

After a long separation, Yuran Mammadov, who found an innumerable source of inspiration for his searches and artistic improvisations in the environment of Nakhchivan, the landscape he created ("Hachadag", "Batabat", "Alinca Castle", "Vaykhur Village", "Araz", "Shahbuz Landscape", "Village", "Gas drawing", "Spring in Nakhchivan", Sarhaddin's guard", etc.) and portraits ("Günel", "Aytan", "Portrait of my wife", etc.) won the admiration of art lovers with the "color games" he demonstrated. Contrasting colors, as in miniatures, are the main meaning-content carriers of these compositions of different genres in these works, which cover the artist's creativity of the seventies. Since the attractiveness of the separate details, realized by the "meeting" of the decorative color surfaces of the

individual lives that join the aesthetics of real artistic principles, is also directed towards the opening of the burden of meaning and content, the images presented to the audience are not only a spiritual resource filled with colors, but also attract attention with their thought-provokingness. As in most of his works, it is possible to witness the artist's symbolic-artistic approach to painting in his painting "Spring in Nakhchivan" (1970s). Thus, the four young women who were brought to the scene in the labor field were also thought of as a sign of the arrival of spring in the land of Ajami. Although there is no sharp dynamics in the movements of the girls in metallic clothes depicted against the background of the heartwarming colors of the motif of reviving and renewing nature, the figures in the moment itself. There is a great hope that the new day will be successful, which begins in its expressive silhouettes. Although a certain contrast can be felt in the general coloring created by different shades of color, the desired artistic integrity of the observed can be felt in the miniature assessment.

The artist's "Awakening" painting belonging to that period also glorifies spring. But here the main meaning-content bearer of the renewal of nature is nature itself. The general view of the blooming trees surrounding the farmland behind the spring-leaved azman trees showing their beauty in the sunny weather against the background of the blue-green colored mountains is quite attractive and emotional. In addition to presenting the land in the foreground, middle, and background in different shades of color, which has been allocated a very large space in the format, the achievement of the integrity of the visible can be considered the result of the author's unusual sense of color without a doubt.

His work "Our Root" created in the seventies is the bearer of a completely different song. Anar, a close friend of the artist and a well-known writer, writes about this painting: "The work dedicated by the artist to the memory of his father is called "Our Root". Two old men sitting side by side are depicted here. Their figures are almost motionless. This is confirmed by tired hands hanging down, bent backs, silence and gazes directed into the distance or into their inner world. Only old people who worship their memories and past for hours can sit like this. The two dead trees depicted in the background give a sharper sense of the sunset of human life" [4, p.445].

Upon his return to Nakhchivan, the artist, who paid close attention to the changes taking place in his native country, created the painting "Gas Shooting" in the seventies. Yuran Mammadov, who wanted to show more prominently the romanticism of labor, which this multi-figure composition is plagued with, gave priority to the hotness created by warm colors in the general color solution of the work. The author, who makes extensive use of different shades of red-orange colors, is one of the builders on their lunch break.

managed to create different images. In this sense, it is necessary to emphasize that the figures with different postures scattered along the canvas are depicted with individual experiences. Therefore, we must say that their surrounding with workers' wagons

and pipes gives a unique character to the labor process experienced here...

Although Yuran Mammadov shows his loyalty to the classical tradition in all genres, it can be seen especially prominently in his works in the landscape genre. Although we have informed about this above, we must say that we encountered a different aesthetic of his searches in this genre in his paintings dedicated to mountain villages. "Midday in the mountains", "Sahab", "Autumn in the mountains", "Village", etc., created by him in the landscape genre. tables are like this.

The artist ("Sahab"), who depicted the evening view of the village of Sahab, located in the heart of the mountains, managed to create a very characteristic image of the village bathed in the dawn of the sun. In the composition of the vertical format, the author, who created an artistic image of the ancient Turkish homeland with the intersection of mountains, flat-roofed houses, autumn "dressed" trees, and oxen returning from the trough to their native yards, demonstrated the ability to expand the "aesthetic map" of the genre as a whole. The artist, who achieved the resonance of the contrast in the unity of contrasting red, orange, yellow and black colors with miniature aesthetics, was able to show the optimistic tone of the work.

Yuran Mammadov's painting "Autumn in the Mountains" also captures the "artistic mirror" of nature's autumn landscape. The artist who turned the square-format composition into a "hot pot" in the literal sense of the word with lush color contrasts, the author who presented various details - farmlands stretching up to the mountains, mulberry trees like flowers "growing" from the soil, orange peaks and clouds "ignited" by the sun. , optimistic creativity has determined the transformation of the image into the image of the place, which is undeniable.

It is possible to witness the unique results of the artist's creative attitude to miniature aesthetics in the plate "At Noon in the Mountains". The perspective chosen by the author to reveal the characteristic features of the mountain village is interesting. As it is here in thumbnails although it is not seen that he follows the principle of direct arrangement, but by looking down on the village houses presented with trees and its street with bulls, he managed to present the viewer with all the beauty of the spaciousness of the space as well as the heart-warming-optimistic aura carried by the image. It is also undeniable that the color "woven" from bright colors gives uniqueness to the overall artistic capacity of the work. In our opinion, the transformation of the entire image into a dominant is primarily an indicator of the elevation of the ordinary motif to the image.

Although a different meaning-content is "hidden" in the name of the work "Guardian of the Border", in reality the artist has created a proud image of Nakhchivan, which stands out for its magnificence. Yuran Mammadov, who created the background of the horizontal composition from the mountains whose peaks are covered with clouds, placed the border guard station and two soldiers in the "light" of the water basin,

which expresses the content of the title of the work, by bringing into view the Araz River, which divides the space into two parts. His creative attitude to miniature aesthetics and his ability to add Eastern spirit to the aesthetics of realism were also noteworthy in the artist's work, which took place in the eighties and covered a very short period of time. The author, who gives a unique artistic interpretation to his thoughts in compositions with different themes "enriched" with color improvisations, ultimately succeeded in creating works that can excite the audience's imagination. His "First Dawn" (1981), "Seville" (1981), "The World of Poetry" (1982), "In Front of the Mirror" (1982), "Oxen" (1983), "Portrait of My Son" (1983), "At the spring" (1983). The paintings "The Pipe Sound" (1984) and "Afternoon" (1984) are of this kind. In these works of his with different plots, the memorable results of finding national artistic resources are visible in the form and form that serve to achieve the compositional integrity of joyful and optimistic colors. "World of Poetry" dedicated to the unique world of Huseyn Javid by the artist the inclusion of the images that make up the creativity of the genius wordsmith in his work was purposeful, as a rule, it aimed to show the richness of the spiritual source, which is notable for its "iceberg". In this approach, which aims to hold an "artistic mirror" to Javid's fate, which is also full of contrasts, the author has given a wise visuality to the carrier of poetic meaning and content, imbued with the aesthetics of romanticism. As a result of the artist's successful use of the emotive power of black, red, white and yellow colors, which make up the color of the composition, "The World of Poetry" is far from lyricism, as many

people think, and shows its focus on thought-provoking.

In Yuran Mammadov's paintings "In front of the mirror", "By the spring", "The sound of the pipe" and "Afternoon", the unique author's attitude towards miniature aesthetics can be felt in the various figures that are the main meaning-content carriers of the compositions. The artist, who turned to the village motif in "The Sound of the Pipe", was able to create an attention-grabbing tableau with its sincerity. The image of the grandfather dreaming of his grandson playing the instrument, the grandmother baking bread against the background of the autumn landscape of the village is quite attractive. "Sevil", "Portrait of my son", "Oxen", etc., where the artist worked in other genres. These works, whose integrity is prominent, are remembered as the bearers of the national spirit due to the creative approach to the traditions of miniature painting, revealing the form in his works. On the whole, if we remember that this kind of approach is characteristic of the artist's works with different themes and genres, then we can say that Yuran Mammadov's artistic heritage is a great example of a creative attitude to the classical tradition.

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